

Impacts of ICT and Social Media platforms on Performance in Economics among students in selected tertiary institutions in Kaduna State

Ubangida, Shuaibu¹

shubyhanwasg@mail.com

08036805194,

Abdullahi, Hadiza¹

, hadizaabdullah72@gmail.com

08066037555

Zakari, Safiyanu Bello¹

safiyanuzakari22@gmail.com

07033500368

¹Department of Economics, Federal College of Education, Zaria

Abstract

This study investigated the impacts of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and social media platforms on the performance of Economics students at selected tertiary institutions in Kaduna State. It aimed to assess the effects of ICT and social media on academic performance and study habits. A total of 450 students were selected from three institutions using a multi-stage sampling technique. Data were collected through questionnaires and analyzed using descriptive statistics and a Probit model. The study used ICT tools (such as computers and educational apps) and social media platforms (Facebook, Twitter, TikTok, WhatsApp) as key variables. Key findings revealed that Facebook usage and the negative consequences of social media significantly reduce academic performance. Conversely, WhatsApp usage and lecturer guidance positively impact academic outcomes. In terms of study habits, collaborative ICT and social media-based activities were found to significantly improve study habits, whereas the negative effects of social media were detrimental to study habits. The research underscores the dual-edged nature of social media in education, highlighting the importance of a balanced integration of ICT and social media. The study rejects the null hypotheses, confirming that both ICT and social media significantly influence academic performance and study habits. It recommends that the government and stakeholders invest in ICT infrastructure, including computers, internet access, and essential software, to foster a technologically enhanced learning environment.

Keywords: Academic Performance, communication, information, social media, technology

Introduction

Social media and ICT can have both beneficial and detrimental effects on students' academic achievement in economics. To understand the specific dynamics at work, a case study in selected tertiary institutions in Kaduna State, or similar regions, could be insightful. ICT plays a crucial role in educational institutions by generating, storing, processing, distributing, and exchanging information (Otuu, 2013). This provides students with access to a wealth of economics-related resources such as online academic journals, instructional videos, and textbooks, facilitating research and study.

ICT tools enhance student interaction with peers and lecturers, improving their understanding of economic concepts through online discussions and clarifications. This networked environment suggests that ICT can significantly enhance teaching and learning efficiency (UNDP Evaluation Office, 2001, in Otuu, 2013). However, the effects of social media and ICT vary based on how students use these tools. While ICT promotes educational equity, accessibility, professional development, and efficient educational management, it also has drawbacks. Social media, for example, can be distracting and lead to academic neglect and social isolation (Andoh, 2012, in Muhammad et al., 2015).

Despite these challenges, ICT offers significant advantages, such as speeding up learning, saving time, and facilitating efficient discussions (Muhammad et al., 2015). However, understanding these dynamics requires a comprehensive examination of student usage patterns. In Nigerian tertiary institutions, the use of computers and Android phones as teaching aids has contributed to a more inclusive classroom environment (Zubair, 2016). Yet, despite

African countries prioritizing ICT in education, progress in its integration remains limited. Only a few schools have effectively incorporated ICT into their curricula, and many teachers remain unaware of available ICT resources, leading to continued low performance in subjects like economics due to poor instructional methods (Ikwuka & Adigwe, 2016; Olojede, Bolaji, & Musa, 2017).

The study aims to investigate specific challenges in economics education and reassess the use of ICT as a teaching aid. It also seeks to explore the under-researched area of educational technology for early education, including online resources for parents, while considering access equity (Greenhow & Lewin, 2021). By collecting data on students' academic performance in economics, the study will evaluate the perceived advantages and disadvantages of ICT and social media.

Previous research has explored various aspects of ICT and social media's impact on academic performance. Notable studies include Karpinski and Duberstein (2009), who examined Facebook usage and academic performance, and Aduwa-Ogiegbaen and Iyamu (2005), who identified barriers to ICT use in Nigerian secondary schools. Peter (2015) investigated social media use and academic achievement at the University of Lagos, while Lauren (2014) discussed the benefits of social media use. Muhammad and Irfan (2015) focused on ICT's impact on students' access to information at Gomal University.

Additionally, Ikwuka and Adigwe (2016) studied ICT's effects on Christian Religious Studies students' performance, and Zubairu (2016) evaluated the impact of internet-based resources on biology performance among senior secondary students in Kaduna State. However, no research has specifically addressed the effects of ICT and social media on economics students' academic performance, highlighting a gap that this study aims to fill.

Objectives of the study

1. To examine the effects of use of ICT on the on academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions.
2. To examine the effects of social media Platforms on the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions.
3. To examine the extent to which the use of ICT and social media affect the study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions

Research Questions

1. How does use of ICT affect the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions?
2. How does the use of social media Platforms affect the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions?
3. To what extent does the use of ICT and social media affect the study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions?

Hypotheses:

The study set three hypotheses as follows:

1. **Null Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁):** Use of ICT has no significant effects on students' performance in Economics students in tertiary institutions.
2. **Null Hypothesis 2 (H₀₂):** Use of social media Platforms has no significant effects on the students' performance in Economics students in tertiary institutions.
3. **Null Hypothesis 3 (H₀₃):** ICT and social media have no significant effects on study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions

Methodology

Research Design

The study used both descriptive and analytical statistics to explore the impact of ICT and social media on students' academic performance in economics at tertiary institutions in Kaduna State. The study adopts a mixed-methods approach using qualitative and quantitative design to assess the ICT resources available for teaching and learning

economics. This approach aims to provide a thorough understanding of how these technologies influence academic outcomes.

Population and Sampling

The study targets economics students from tertiary institutions in Kaduna State during 2023/2024 academic session. Three institutions were selected using multi-stage sampling technique to represent the state's higher education landscape: Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria; Kaduna State University, Kaduna; and College of Education, Gidan Waya, Kafanchan. Each institution contributed 150 students which gives a sample size of 450 students, which is considered adequate for the study.

Method of Data Collection

Surveys, questionnaires, interviews, and academic records were used to collect data for the study. These techniques are selected in order find more about how students utilise ICT and social media to foster their academic achievement.

Validation of Research Instrument

The instruments were developed by the researcher and evaluated by experts from the Departments of Economics and Computer Education at Federal College of Education, Zaria. Content validity was used in this investigation, a sort of validity that indicates how much the study's objectives and research questions are represented. The researchers requested experts to assess the relevance of the test items in measuring the study variables. To make the instruments better, their opinions, clarifications, and ideas were noted and effected.

Reliability of Research Instrument

Pilot study was carried out in Federal College of Education, Zaria, and Nuhu Bamalli Polytechnic, Zaria. The questionnaire was distributed to 60 individuals who were not part of the selected group. Consequently, a reliability index of 0.70 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test indicating that the instrument is reliable for the study.

Method of Data Analysis

Both descriptive and inferential statistics will be used. Descriptive statistics include measures like mean and standard deviation. Inferential analysis used the Probit model to examine the impact of ICT and social media on academic performance and study habits. The study used descriptive statistics to answer the research questions and three Probit Regression models and test the hypotheses of the study. The general Probit model is given as:

$$p(Y = 1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 ICT + \beta_2 SM + \beta_k Control_k + \varepsilon$$

Where $p(Y = 1)$ is the probability of success (academic performance), Φ is the cumulative distribution function of the standard normal distribution, $\beta_0, \beta_1, \beta_2$ and β_k are the coefficients to be estimated. Based on the objectives of this study, the above model is transformed and broken into three different models adapted from the study of Muawiya, Ubangida and Zakari (2023) as follows:

Model 1: $p(ACDPERF = 1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 UICT + \beta_2 UCP + \beta_3 EDUAP + \beta_4 ONLT + \beta_5 LICT + \beta_6 IICT + \varepsilon_1)$ ----- 1

This model was used to examine the effect of ICT tools and usage frequency on academic performance. The dependent variable is students' academic performance, measured by changes in their CGPA. Independent variables include the frequency of ICT usage (UICT), use of computers/laptops (UCP), educational apps (EDUAP), online tutorials (ONLT), and lecturers incorporating ICT in teaching (LICT). The model also includes a control variable representing improved performance due to ICT use (IICT).

Model 2: $p(ACDPERF = 1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 USM + \beta_2 fb + \beta_3 X + \beta_4 I + \beta_5 TT + \beta_6 W + \beta_6 LISM + \beta_6 CSM + \varepsilon_1)$ ----- 2

This model was used to analyze the impact of social media usage on academic performance. The dependent variable remains academic performance. The independent variables of interest are the frequency of social media usage (USM) and specific platforms like Facebook (fb), Twitter (X), Instagram (I), TikTok (TT), and WhatsApp (W). Improved performance due to social media (ISM) and the consequences of social media (CSM) serve as control variables.

Model 3: $p(SH=1) = \Phi(\beta_0 + \beta_1 SICT + \beta_2 SSM + \beta_3 IICT + \beta_3 ISM + \beta_4 I + \beta_5 CSM + \varepsilon_3)$ -----3

This model was used to investigate the influence of ICT and social media on students' study habits (SH). Independent variables include studying Economics through collaborative ICT-based activities (SICT), social media-based activities (SSM), improved performance due to ICT (IICT), and social media platforms (ISM). Increased interest in learning due to ICT and social media (I) and the consequences of social media (CSM) are used as control variables. Each model estimates the coefficients (β_i) of the independent variables and includes a disturbance term (ε) to account for variability not explained by the model.

Results

Research Question 1: How does use of ICT affect the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions?

Table 1 Descriptive Statistics: Effect of ICT on Academic Performance

Variables	Mean	Std Dev	Decision (Effect)
Usage rate of ICT (UICT)	0.528	0.206	moderate
Usage of Computers/Phones (UCP):	0.697	0.194	high
Usage of Educational Apps (EDUAPP)	0.593	0.305	moderate
Online Teaching and Learning (ONLT)	0.826	0.223	high
Lecturers Involving ICT in teaching (LICT)	0.535	0.463	moderate
Improved Performance dues to ICT (IICT)	0.773	0.264	high
Usage rate of ICT (UICT)	0.528	0.506	Moderate

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

Table 1 presents descriptive statistics on the impact of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) on academic performance. The average ICT usage rate is moderate (mean = 0.528) with low variability (standard deviation = 0.206). Computer and phone usage is high (mean = 0.697) and consistent across students (standard deviation = 0.194). Educational app usage is moderate (mean = 0.593) but shows higher variability (standard deviation = 0.305), indicating diverse usage patterns. Online teaching and learning have a high adoption rate (mean = 0.826) with low variability (standard deviation = 0.223), reflecting consistent use. Lecturers' involvement in using ICT for teaching is moderate (mean = 0.535) with significant variability (standard deviation = 0.463), suggesting differing levels of engagement. ICT is perceived to significantly improve academic performance (mean = 0.773) with moderate variability (standard deviation = 0.264), indicating that this benefit is somewhat uniformly experienced.

In summary, ICT usage is widespread among students, particularly through computers, phones, and online teaching, and is generally seen as enhancing academic performance. However, there is variability in lecturers' involvement and in the use of educational apps, suggesting areas where consistency could be improved.

Null Hypothesis 1 (H₀₁):

Use of ICT has no significant effect on students' performance in Economics students in tertiary institutions.

Table 2: Results for Probit Regression Model 1

Dependent Variable: Academic Performance (ACDPERF)

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
<i>UICT</i>	0.295047	0.120888	2.440664	0.0166
<i>UCP</i>	0.393699	0.124734	3.156309	0.0025
<i>EDUAPP</i>	0.223182	0.116359	1.918042	0.0551
<i>ONLT</i>	0.318935	0.111533	2.859563	0.0042
<i>LICT</i>	0.029319	0.113503	0.258311	0.7962
<i>IICT</i>	0.137845	0.118623	1.162039	0.2452

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

In Table 2, Academic Performance is analyzed as the dependent variable: A one-unit increase in UICT is associated with a 0.295047 unit increase in Academic Performance ($z = 2.440664$, $p = 0.0166$), indicating a statistically significant effect. A one-unit increase in UCP leads to a 0.393699 unit increase in Academic Performance ($z = 3.156309$, $p = 0.0025$), showing a statistically significant impact. A one-unit increase in EDUAPP corresponds to a 0.223182 unit increase in Academic Performance, but the p-value (0.0551) is slightly above the 0.05 significance level, making it marginally significant. A one-unit increase in ONLT results in a 0.318935 unit increase in Academic Performance ($z = 2.859563$, $p = 0.0042$), indicating a statistically significant effect. With a coefficient of 0.029319, LICT is not a statistically significant predictor ($p = 0.7962$). IICT has a coefficient of 0.137845 but is not statistically significant ($p =$

0.2452). Overall, most variables significantly predict Academic Performance, leading to the rejection of Null hypothesis H01. The direction of the relationships is determined by the sign of the coefficients.

Research Question 2: How does the use of social media Platforms affect the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institutions?

Table 3: Descriptive Statistics: Effect of social media Platforms on academic performance

Variables	Mean	Std Dev	Decision (Effect)
Social media usage USM	0.740	0.584	High
Facebook (fb)	0.678	0.496	High
Twitter (X)	0.211	0.301	Very Low
TikTok (TT)	0.398	0.500	Very low
WhatsApp (W)	0.967	0.440	High
Lecturer Support and Guidance (LSM)	0.531	0.663	Moderate
Consequences of Social Media (CSM)	0.601	0.512	High

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

Table 3 presents descriptive statistics on the effect of social media platforms on academic performance, including the overall usage of social media, specific platforms, and related factors. The descriptive statistics indicate that social media platforms generally have a positive impact on academic performance, though the degree of this effect varies. Social Media Usage (USM) has a high negative effect with a mean of 0.740 and a standard deviation of 0.584, indicating some variability in its impact. Facebook (mean: 0.678, SD: 0.496) also has a high positive effect with moderate variability. Twitter (mean: 0.211, SD: 0.301) and TikTok (mean: 0.398, SD: 0.500) show lower positive effects, with Twitter having the lowest impact and least variability. WhatsApp has the highest positive effect (mean: 0.967, SD: 0.440), suggesting it is the most beneficial. Lecturer Support (mean: 0.531, SD: 0.663) shows a moderate positive effect, with significant variability. The Consequences of Social Media (mean: 0.301, SD: 0.512) reveal a low negative effect, with moderate variability in its impact. Overall, while most platforms have a positive effect, WhatsApp and general social media usage are the most beneficial, and the negative effects of social media are relatively low.

Null Hypothesis 2: Use of social media Platforms has no significant effect on the students' performance in Economics students in tertiary institutions

Table 4: Results for Probit Regression Model 2

Dependent Variable: Academic Performance (ACDPERF)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
USM	-1.424618	0.124928	11.40349	0.0412
Fb	-0.264500	0.126977	-2.083052	0.0372
X	0.477820	0.119231	4.007507	0.2001
TT	-0.077536	0.120560	-0.643137	0.5201
W	0.438415	0.115502	2.497056	0.0041
LSM	0.264807	0.112260	2.358872	0.0037
CSM	0.430200	0.129247	3.328519	0.0009

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

The Probit model in Table 4 evaluates the impact of various factors on Academic Performance: A one-unit increase decreases Academic Performance by 1.424618 units ($z = 1.40349$, $p = 0.0412$), showing a significant negative effect. A one-unit increase reduces Academic Performance by 0.264500 units ($z = 2.083052$, $p = 0.0372$), indicating a statistically significant negative impact. A one-unit increase increases Academic Performance by 0.477820 units, but this effect is not statistically significant ($z = 1.007507$, $p = 0.2001$). A one-unit increase decreases Academic Performance by 0.077536 units, which is not statistically significant ($z = -0.643137$, $p = 0.5201$). A one-unit increase improves Academic Performance by 0.438415 units ($z = 2.497056$, $p = 0.0041$), indicating a statistically significant positive effect. A one-unit increase boosts Academic Performance by 0.264807 units ($z = 2.358872$, $p = 0.0037$), showing a statistically significant positive effect. A one-unit increase decreases Academic Performance by 0.430200 units ($z =$

3.328519, $p = 0.0009$), indicating a significant negative effect. Thus, most variables significantly impact Academic Performance, with clear directionality in their effects, leading to the rejection of the Null hypothesis H02.

Research Question 3: To what extent does the use of ICT and social media affect the study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions?

Table 5: Descriptive Statistics: Effect of ICT and social media affect the study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions

Variables	Mean	Std Dev	Decision (Effect)
SICT (Study Economics through Collaborative ICT-Based activities)	0.640	0.484	High
SSM (Study Economics through Collaborative Social media-Based activities)	0.678	0.496	High
IICT (Improved Performance due to ICT),	0.511	0.401	Moderate
ISM (Improved Performance and social media)	0.398	0.500	Low
I (Increased Interest in learning due to use of ICT and Social Media),	0.767	0.440	High
Consequences of Social Media (CSM)	0.501	0.503	Moderate

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

The average score of 0.640 suggests that students generally have a positive experience with collaborative ICT-based activities in economics, though variability is moderate ($SD = 0.484$). Social media-based activities also show a positive outcome with a mean score of 0.678 and similar variability ($SD = 0.496$), indicating they are highly effective in enhancing learning. ICT usage moderately improves performance (Mean = 0.511, $SD = 0.401$), while social media has a lower impact on performance (Mean = 0.398, $SD = 0.500$) with high variability. The use of ICT and social media significantly increases interest in learning (Mean = 0.767, $SD = 0.440$), and the consequences of social media have a moderate effect (Mean = 0.501, $SD = 0.503$) with considerable variability. Overall, ICT and social media enhance learning and interest, though their impact on performance and consequences varies.

Null Hypothesis 3 (H03): ICT and social media have no significant affect on study habits of Economics students in tertiary institutions

Table 6:

Results for Probit Model 3

Dependent Variable: Study Habit (SH)				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	z-Statistic	Prob.
SICT	0.432415	0.115502	3.497056	0.0241
SSM	0.234807	0.112260	2.338872	0.0237
IICT	0.422220	0.129247	3.222519	0.0209
ISM	0.355557	0.144880	2.445322	0.0170
I	0.493699	0.124734	3.446309	0.0325
CSM	-0.623182	0.116359	4.918042	0.0251

Source: Field Survey and Computation using E-View 10

The results of the Probit model in Table 6 examines how various factors influence study habits. Key findings include. For **SICT**, a one-unit increase in SICT raises study habits by 0.432415 units ($z = 3.497056$, $p = 0.0241$), showing it is a significant predictor. A one-unit increase in SSM boosts study habits by 0.234807 units ($z = 2.338872$, $p = 0.0237$), also statistically significant. A one-unit increase in IICT enhances study habits by 0.422220 units ($z = 3.222519$, $p = 0.0209$), indicating high significance. A one-unit increase in ISM results in a 0.355557 unit increase in study habits ($z = 2.445322$, $p = 0.0070$), showing significant predictive power. A one-unit rise in interest increases study habits by 0.493699 units ($z = 3.446309$, $p = 0.0325$), likely significant. A one-unit increase in CSM decreases study habits by 0.623182 units ($z = 2.625$, $p = 0.025$), indicating a significant negative impact. Thus, all variables significantly predict study habits, leading to the rejection of the Null hypothesis H03.

Discussion of Findings

The relationship and effects of ICT on the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institution revealed the presence of a significant relationship and effect for majority of the variable examined in this study. The findings are in conformity with the findings of Ikwuka and Adigwe (2016); Zubairu (2016), Olojede, Bolaji and Musa (2017), Pedro & Kumar (2020 and Jamal & Nawab (2020). However, Ikwuka and Adigwe (2016) Zubairu (2016) conducted their studies on the academic performance of Secondary School students in CRS and Biology respectively.

The relationship and effects of Social Media usage on the academic performance of Economics students in tertiary institution revealed the presence of a significant relationship and effect for majority of the variable examined in this study. The findings from this study are in conformity with the findings of Waleed, Mohd & Lizawati (2015); Greenhow, C., & Lewin, C. (2016), Ansari & Khan (2020) Pedro & Kumar (2020), Jamal & Nawab (2020), Osuji & Wokoma (2023), Anita (2024) and Lene Et al (2024). However, although, Ansari & Khan (2020) study revealed and concluded that social media could distract students, social media provided valuable platforms for academic discussion and resource sharing, ultimately benefiting those who used it effectively

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The study also revealed that a positive significant relationship exist between study habit and usage of ICT and social media. However, it has been observed that, the consequences of social media usage led to dissatisfaction and Isolation from others, distraction from learning and unnecessary fatigue to the users, laziness and fatigue impact negatively on study habit. This finding is in line with that of Ansari & Khan (2020) and many other studies on the effects of social media on students' performance.

Conclusion

The study on the effects of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and Social Media Usage on the academic performance of pupils in mathematics at selected tertiary institutions in Kaduna State sheds light on the link between technology and education. Based on the study of quantitative and qualitative data, the findings reveal how the use of ICT tools and social media platforms a favourably relates with students' academic achievement in Economics. Students that use technological tools such as laptops, androids, social media platforms, online application improve their motivation and study habits, as well as their understanding of Economics leading to improvement in their academic performance. Despite the excellent outcomes, there are still hurdles to implementing ICT in Economics education, such as infrastructural limits, access inequities and the need for teacher training to mention just a few challenges. These problems can prevent students from fully utilising the benefits of technology in their study.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

1. Government and other stakeholders should prioritise investing in ICT infrastructure in Education. Adequate provision of computers, internet access, and essential software is critical for establishing a technologically enabled learning environment.
2. Efforts should be made by government and other stakeholders to guarantee that all students have fair access to ICT resources while addressing socioeconomic gaps. Initiatives like giving laptop computers, internet access, and digital learning materials can help close the digital gap.
3. Efforts should be made to ensure implementation of comprehensive training programs to equip teachers with the knowledge and confidence to successfully integrate ICT into their teaching methods.
4. Educational policymakers should work with educators to create curriculum modules that match with both technological improvements and pedagogical objectives.
5. Establish regular monitoring and assessment systems to examine ICT integration's impact on academic performance. This includes receiving feedback from teachers and students to help guide future changes and adjustments.

Acknowledgements

The research work was supported by Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFUND), Federal Republic of Nigeria. It was financially supported by IBR TETFund Research Project (Batch-10, 2024).

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